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Abstract:

These guidelines detail the data collection process for Audio capture data in social surveys. The aim is to collect audio capture data from social surveys that is of sufficient quality for analysis as digital language data.

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Executive Summary

These guidelines set out the rationale and design of a computer assisted recorded interview module for a social survey. The aim of this module is to capture digital language data from a traditional social survey interview and therefore illustrate the potential complementarities between linguistic and social survey infrastructures. The guidelines provide an overview of the background associated with the modules development and the specifications for the data generated from both a survey research and linguistic perspective. These requirements are then integrated into technical requirements for the module and the module itself is detailed.

These guidelines were developed by researchers from CLARIN, the Generations & Gender Programme and the European Values Study. The researchers discussed the various requirements of both survey infrastructures and linguistic infrastructures and the potential benefits of utilising services from each other's operations. The overarching aim of this work is to demonstrate the potential application of CLARIN tools, resources and services in survey research and the utilization of survey infrastructure and data collection technologies for collecting digital language data.

The guidelines will be taken forward and applied within an appropriate survey infrastructure in the remainder of the SSHOC project. The data generated from this data collection will then be transferred to CLARIN for processing, as a proof of concept for the cross-pollination of services between social science and humanities research infrastructures. The guidelines will then be refined and published in light of the results of the data collection and used as a template for future synthesis of survey infrastructures and the collection and processing of digital language data.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
SSHOC	Social Science & Humanities Open Cloud
GGP	Generations & Gender Programme
EVS	European Values Study
ESS	European Social Survey
SHARE	Survey of Health Ageing & Retirement in Europe
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
DANS	Data Archiving & Networked Services (NL)
NIDI	Netherlands Interdisciplinary Demographic Institute
CATI	Computer Assisted Telephone Interviews
PAPI	Paper and Pencil Interviews
CAPI	Computer Assisted Personal Interviews
CARI	Computer Assisted Recorded Interviews
CAWI	Computer Assisted Web Interviews
ASR	Automatic Speech Recognition
NLP	Natural Language Processing
AAC	Advanced Audio Coding

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1. Introduction

This deliverable is the first associated with *Task 4.4. Voice recorded interviews and audio analysis* in the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud project (SSHOC). This task will collect audio data in the form of voice recorded interviews from the Generations and Gender Survey. This audio data will then be processed and analysed by colleagues at CLARIN to contribute with automatic speech recognition, speaker attribution, part-of-speech-tagging, named entity labelling and other NLP tools. Survey methodologists and Social Scientists from the EVS and GGP will work together with data scientists and oral historians from CLARIN to develop a survey module specifically adapted to integrate audio recordings and their processing into the traditional data collection process. Thematically they will focus on the qualitative assessment of value statements. Once fielded, CLARIN will adapt existing auto-transcription tools to the specific needs of the audio survey data and make the transcribed files available for analysis. Data Archiving and Networked Services (NL) (DANS-KNAW) will oversee archiving and dissemination of the data, drawing on their significant experience with oral histories.

In these guidelines, we set out the questionnaire and fieldwork principles for the implementation of the Audio Survey Modules. These will then be implemented in fieldwork in early 2021 and the data processed and analysed before the end of 2021 (Month 36 of the project). A specific questionnaire and guidelines are required as the aim of the project is unprecedented in several respects: Audio data is sometimes captured by surveys as part of data quality control, but the technical implementation and questionnaire content are rarely if ever optimized to ensure that the digital language data generated from the interview is optimized for linguistic analysis. What is unique about this task is that researchers from CLARIN were involved from the early stages of design in order to ensure that the substantive focus and technical implementation of the project would be able to produce audio data and transcripts that produce meaningful results when analysed with the tools at CLARIN's disposal.

These guidelines proceed as follows. First, the various aims of the project are outlined from the perspective of survey infrastructures (GGP & EVS) and linguistic infrastructures (CLARIN). These, help shape the technical requirements that are then laid out in section 4. Finally, the questions which we intend to field are then laid out.

2. The Survey Perspective

Social surveys have been predominantly conducted as **Computer Assisted Personal Interviews (CAPI)** since the 1990's (Baker, 1992). In this context, the interviewer has the interview script loaded onto a computer or mobile device and then asks the questions as they appear on the screen, and inputs the answers provided by the respondents. This approach replaced the Paper and Pencil Interview (PAPI) and led to significant improvements in data processing and data quality (Laurie, 2003). With the improved performance and capabilities of computers, and particularly the prevalence of devices such as tablets and laptops with in-built microphones, **Computer Assisted Recorded Interviews (CARI)** have become increasingly prevalent (Hicks et al., 2010). In this context a CAPI program would run, but audio data would be captured alongside it.

Conventionally, this audio data was only captured on specific survey items for which the survey administrators wanted additional oversight or control (Thissen & Nguyen, 2013). This is because the primary function of CARI methods has been in the area of **quality control in surveys**. One of the biggest risks in a large-scale survey is *interviewer fraud* (Thissen & Myers, 2016). This can occur when interviewers say they have conducted an interview but have instead falsified data. This form of fraud has been regulated by the requirement of GPS devices which record whether the interviewer was at the correct address or not, or via call backs in which a proportion of the sample are contacted to check whether they actually completed an interview with the interviewer as reported.

A far harder form of fraud to detect is manipulation with the script to shorten the duration of interviews. Given that most interviewers are paid based on how many interviews they have completed, they have an incentive to make the interviews as short as possible. Many surveys include complex routing which can be tiresome and lengthy to complete (Gauthier, Cabaço, & Emery, 2018). Given that most interviewers become well acquainted with the interview structure, it is easy for them to forge single responses to questions and circumvent large parts of the questionnaire. For example, in the Generations and Gender Programme interviewers quickly learnt that if they reported that the respondent had no children or were living alone, large parts of the questionnaire would be skipped (Ruckdeschel, Sauer, & Naderi, 2016).

To circumvent this CARI methods are regularly deployed on specific questions to check whether interviewers are administering vital elements of the questionnaire correctly. CARI methods are particularly common in Computer Assisted Telephone Interviews (CATI) given the prevalence of audio data processing in phone banks generally. However, in CATI the role of CARI as a data quality evaluation device is also dominant. CARI has yet to be extensively used for the augmentation of the substantive aims of the survey itself. Audio data contains a large amount of information beyond the information that can be captured by the coding of the data into quantifiable information (Singer & Couper, 2017). Beyond data quality verification, we identify three levels of data that could potentially be extracted from audio data collected in interviews.

First, the audio data collected could be used for **validation of target concepts**. The audio data could allow for semantic mapping of categories beyond those included in the CAPI script and potentially reveal a broader conceptual basis than allowed for by the questionnaire design. For example, survey researchers regularly struggle with the validity and reliability of items measuring institutional trust (Jagodzinski & Manabe, 2004). When asked whether they generally trust other people, respondents might regularly use synonyms like ‘hope’ and ‘rely’ that might help survey researchers better understand the respondents conceptual understanding of the question and the underlying meaning of their response.

Second, the audio data could be used to assess **sentiment of respondents** (US12/481, 2009). This could serve to evaluate respondent experience by identifying speech that is cooperative or non-cooperative (valence). It could also be used to provide substantive insights into respondent’s attitudes towards topics (arousal). This has been used extensively in the private sector, specifically within phone companies running automated speech recognition systems to process customers (Sehgal, Agarwal, & Rai, 2018). Such data potentially provides valuable information when assessing individuals’ sentiments both towards the interview generally and specific topics covered by the survey. In many social surveys, sentiment is directly asked with regards to a wide range of topics and these can be used to validate the audio data. For example, the European Values Study includes a battery of questions on the future direction of the country (Dickes & Valentova, 2013). Sentiment during the section of the survey could be validated on the reported levels of positivity expressed by the respondent.

Finally, there are a **broader set of substantive variables** of interest that could potentially be extracted from the data. These are of general substantive interest but not specifically related to the question specifically delivered in the questionnaire. Such variables include vocabulary depth, speech rate, fluency, clarity and the identification of specific linguistic traits associated with social variables such as region of origin, socio-economic status or underlying health (Rektorova et al., 2016). Such data could be used to gain insights into a wide range of latent concepts that are of central relevance to studies such as the Generations and Gender Programme, the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe, the European Social Survey and the European Values Study. Analysis of such data and the specifications required of data to conduct this analysis is however not well established and the feasibility is poorly laid out.

From the Survey infrastructures perspective, it is therefore essential within this task that data requirements are set out and tested in order to establish the feasibility of using survey and linguistic infrastructures in combination. The **cross-utilisation of infrastructure services** is a key aim of the European Open Science Cloud and this task aims to set out the interoperability guidelines for achieving this ambitious aim.

3. The Linguistics Perspective

Unlike survey infrastructures, linguistic infrastructures such as CLARIN do not conduct data collection. CLARIN provides services, tools and resources to linguistic scholars and researchers for use in their analysis (Váradi, Wittenburg, Krauwer, Wynne, & Koskeniemi, 2008). With regards to data collection, CLARIN is a facilitator and not a director as ESS, SHARE, GGP or EVS. If a theme or geographical area of linguistic data is not covered by the existing digital language data that is available, filling that gap falls outside the remit of CLARIN. CLARIN targets the curation and sharing of existing resources on a thematic, rather than a geographical basis. In ESS, SHARE, GGP or EVS there is a core mission which is to increase the geographical coverage of data collected and ensure that the thematic focus of that data fits with research and policy needs. In this regard the **survey infrastructures have an active role in data collection, and linguistic infrastructures are generally passive**. This distinction stems from the nature of the data that is collected and how it is used in answering the scientific questions that concern the different infrastructures. In survey infrastructures the emphasis is on comparability so that cross-national comparisons can be made that inform policy making at the national and European level. Given this, centralised control is required during the data collection process. Similarly, the survey process is itself expensive and there are large economies of scale in survey research that are suited to a centralized data collection operation within a European Research Infrastructure framework (Emery, 2019).

By contrast, linguistic analysis is generally orientated on context specific questions which require the adaptation of generic tools and methodologies. Similarly, the economies of scale in the collection of linguistic data are relatively limited. Linguistic infrastructures such as CLARIN therefore **focus on tooling researchers** in the harvesting and collection of data for analysis and the various steps involved within processing, analysis and archiving of digital language data (Odijk, 2018). The differences between linguistic and survey infrastructures are therefore grounded in the needs of their respective research communities and are entirely fit for purpose.

However, the nature of survey infrastructures and their pre-existing commitment to nationally representative and comparative data collection potentially provide a vehicle by which linguistic infrastructures could collect digital language data without incurring the large costs that scaling up and standardizing data collection would entail. By collecting audio data and transcripts from social surveys across Europe it could be possible for CLARIN to capture large amounts of high-quality data at limited or no extra costs. There are several advantages that such an approach could have that could be of value to scholars interested in studying language in the European Research Area.

Firstly, the surveys collect representative data and could improve the coverage of marginalized and hard to reach populations. A considerable amount of digital language data is either taken from publicly available media or through small scale studies of populations which are not sampled in a probabilistic manner. This means that the analysis of digital language data tends not to be representative of the whole population (Williams, 2002). Survey infrastructures by contrast go to great lengths to ensure that the data

collected is **representative of the whole of society** and that subsequent analysis can be used to generalise to whole populations and specific sub-groups.

Secondly, the analysis of digital language data generally requires significant adaptation to specific contexts and the precise technical and environmental context in which the recording took place. This can affect data quality and the types of analysis that are possible with the resulting data. CLARIN provides a wide range of flexible tools that are adaptable to specific contexts and fit with this research model. Using the survey infrastructures would allow for the **standardisation of data collection** and a greater deal of homogeneity in the data collected. SHARE for example requires very specific requirements for the devices used in fieldwork and includes intensive interviewer training that ensures that the data collected across the 28 participating countries is as standardized as possible (Malter & Börsch-Supan, 2013). By building on the standardization and ex-ante harmonization in survey infrastructures it might be possible to increase the scale of comparable and harmonized digital linguistic data available to scholars. For example, those studying German speakers could draw on standardized data from thousands of German speakers in Germany, Switzerland, Austria, Luxembourg and Belgium.

Finally, those analysing the digital language data will also have access to a wide range of data that is rarely linked to digital language data. This includes the responses to the surveys themselves but also to administrative data and health records. **Validating models of linguistic data** is a persistent challenge in the field given the lack of context that is usually provided with such data. This is regularly limited to simple metadata that provides limited information on the subject. By using the social surveys to collect linguistic data, scholars would gain access to thousands of variables on which to validate their data. For example, those interested in the speech patterns of the elderly and their association with cognitive decline would be able to use many of the validated scales of cognitive function that are available in surveys such as SHARE. Furthermore, many social surveys are longitudinal, and it could be possible to then identify if audio data on individual's speech could be used to predict future cognitive performance levels or the appearance of specific neurological conditions. With regards to sentiment and values, the social surveys have highly validated scales on attitudes and values that can be incorporated into the modelling of digital language data.

For linguistic infrastructures such as CLARIN, the utilisation of survey infrastructures to collect digital language data allows it to reach a degree of scale and standardisation that has thus far been too costly to be justifiable. There is a clear potential for the use of the data generated by social surveys through CARI but the feasibility is yet to be established. The degree of standardisation across interviews and its effect on data quality and interoperability is yet unknown. The type of data that can be elicited in a general social survey is also largely unknown. Given this, the subsequent value of this approach for language scholars is also unknown. However, the cross-utilisation of services is at the core of the European Open Science Cloud vision and the potential to leverage this for the advancement of science is a key aim of EOSC and this task.

4. Technical Specifications

To maximise the probability of success within the task, the participants (GGP, EVS, CLARIN) met several times to discuss the requirements from both a linguistic and survey perspective. This section lays out the results of this discussion and the technical specifications for the proof of concept that will be delivered by M36 of the SSHOC project. We start by discussing the technical requirements for data collection, then outline the parameters of the data that is required by both parties and finally outline the archiving and storage requirements.

4.1. Data Collection

From the survey perspective, the data collection must be done using software with integrated CARI functionality. The Generations and Gender Programme uses Blaise 5.6¹ to conduct interviews which does carry this functionality (Emery, Cabaço, Lugtig, Toepoel, & Lück, 2019). Audio data is AAC encoded to optimize the relation between audio quality and storage size. The encoded data is saved server side, together with its metadata, including session, fieldname and timing information. Although SQLite² is the default database, CARI supports the Blaise General Data Interface³ allowing the configuration of any of the available Database Management Suite.

The specification of mode in which the survey is administered in is where the technical requirements become problematic. Most social surveys in Europe are traditionally face to face surveys, meaning that an interview is conducted in person between the respondent and interviewer on a device that meets strict specifications and is allocated to the interviewer by the fieldwork team. However, the use of face to face interviews is in steep decline and response rates to face to face surveys are falling. Surveys are therefore becoming increasingly reliant on the use of web administered surveys where the respondent completes the interview on a computer or other internet enabled device (Emery, 2019).

The implications of mode choice for this experiment are crucial. On the one hand, the standardisation and data quality will be higher in the controlled settings of face to face interviews. On the other hand, the decreasing number of face-to-face surveys means that research would be conducted in an environment that is increasingly rare. Furthermore, the tools that will be applied as part of this task by CLARIN vary in their sophistication and maturity depending on the language to which they are applied. These tools are adapted for each language and the quality and maturity of these tools therefore varies

¹ <https://blaise.com/products/blaise-5>

² <https://www.sqlite.org/index.html>

³ <https://blaise.com/products/general-information/14-products/blaise>

across countries. This maturity is roughly inverse to the propensity of a survey infrastructure to field a survey in a face to face setting. The more mature tools are in countries with a well-developed digital infrastructure and research community and these are also the forerunners in adopting web surveys.

4.2. The Dutch Use Case

Given the location of the partners involved in this task, the Netherlands was identified as an optimal candidate for testing the initial implementation of CARI data collection. The Netherlands is an early adopter in the use of web surveys. It hosts an online panel for survey experiments (the LISS panel; (Scherpenzeel, 2016)) and its major surveys are conducted online. There are exceptions to this as the ESS and SHARE are both administered face to face. However, tendering for face to face fieldwork is increasing costs in country and makes the future of face to face surveys very uncertain. Given this, the Dutch Generations and Gender Survey and the Dutch European Values Study are both designed as predominantly online surveys. Furthermore, from the perspective of CLARIN, high quality speech technology tools such as automatic speech recognition (ASR) for Dutch are available in the infrastructure⁴.

The selection of mode for the experiment is therefore with a preference for face to face data collection, but with the probability that this will not be an option given fieldwork constraints. The fieldwork schedule for the Netherlands in 2021 will be known in spring 2020 when the fieldwork budgets are agreed and at this point it will be possible to determine the feasibility of face to face data collection and the survey to which the audio module will be attached. Prior to this, KNAW will produce test case data on its existing infrastructure. This will include around 10 web respondents and 10 face-to-face respondents which will help determine the expected differences in quality of data between modes and the general technical implementation of the module.

If the data is collected in face-to-face mode, it is expected that the devices used in the interviews will record the data in stereo (to avoid speaker overlaps in one audio channel) and interviewers will be specifically instructed to conduct the interview in an area with minimal background noise. Interviewers are already instructed to conduct the interview alone, in a quiet environment but during training they will be informed about the recording and that the elimination of background noises is therefore particularly important.

If the interview is conducted online, there is no control over the type of microphone used and the capacity to record in stereo is not necessarily enforceable. On the positive side, the speech of the respondent will be captured in a single audio channel and speech overlaps with the interviewer will be absent. However,

⁴ See e.g. <https://clarin.phonetik.uni-muenchen.de/apps/oh-portal/>

lack of microphone control in an online setting is particularly problematic given the range of devices used by survey respondents during the survey (Lugtig & Toepoel, 2016). Participants will also be instructed to sit somewhere quiet and with minimal background noise, but this is difficult to enforce. This is therefore likely to worsen the quality of the data collected but the extent to which this is the case is currently unknown. To try and mitigate these effects, respondents will be encouraged to use a microphone or headset device to improve the quality of the recording, although this will not be enforceable.

4.3. Data Specifications

After consultation with CLARIN, it was agreed that the experiment should aim to capture approximately 1,000 spoken words per respondent. This would enable the digital language data to be analysed for the various variables outlined in the previous sections of these guidelines. The team also had to specify whether the vocabulary used would be generic or specific to a theme. Given the nature of the GGP and EVS it would be difficult to field questions on topics such as medicine for which specific vocabularies exist. This is because the sub-population to which these questions could be fielded would be small and would be inefficient in the design of the survey. It was therefore decided that the questions should be aimed at general topics and utilize a general vocabulary database for analysis.

To make full use of the tools and resources available within CLARIN and the novelties of the approach, it was decided that a new ASR module would be designed that would try to elicit detailed verbal responses on topics which are already covered within existing surveys (Singer & Couper, 2017). Given that the average rate of speaking is between 120-150 words per minute, it was envisaged that the design of the module should be around 10 minutes and consist of 8-10 questions with a minimum word count of 100 words. If respondents provided an answer that was less than this, they would be prompted to elaborate. This should provide sufficient data to analyse the basic traits of respondents' speech and also allow for the responses to be validated against pre-existing and established survey response items.

4.4. Data Archiving and Storage

Once data collection is complete, the AAC audio data will be removed from the server and archived at DANS (<http://dans.knaw.nl/>) alongside the Generations and Gender Programme data. This data will not be generally available as it would create a very high risk of data disclosure and respondents could be easily identified from their voice or information contained within the recording. The data will then be transcribed through ASR and processed by the researchers at CLARIN, after the signing of a data agreement which outlines their responsibilities as a data processor under GDPR. This is a standard agreement within the GGP and requires data processors to destroy the data after processing and not process the data except for the reasons explicitly laid out in the agreement. It also prohibits efforts to reidentify respondents and lays out the minimum safe storage procedures required.

Once CLARIN has processed the data, any resulting data will be assessed by the GGP team for disclosure risks and data reduction approaches will be applied where necessary. At this point the general survey data and variables stemming from the analysis of digital language data will be released. At no point will the transcribed data or original audio files be released, and they will not be shared outside of the researchers at CLARIN and GGP (NIDI).

During the interview respondents will be informed that an audio recording will be part of the interview and the archiving and storage process for this process will be detailed as part of the general survey introduction. This information will also be available on the survey landing page and validated by the data protection officer at the Dutch Royal Academy of Science and Art.

5. Audio Module to be fielded

The questions created for the experiment in the SSHOC framework will address the following topics: **Trust, Democracy, and European culture**. These were inspired by the European Values Study items that have a significant degree of conceptual abstraction. More specifically, the aims are, on one side, to assess the comprehension of the respondent of the question and the use of synonyms, and on the other, to identify sentiments that the respondent develops when asked such questions. The responses to all questions can then be pooled and used for generic analysis of the digital language data.

The questions to be used in the CARI module alongside the original EVS questions will be structured as follows:

- an introductory text
- the comprehension question
- the sentiment question.

For each question a pop-up message will appear in the case the respondent does not achieve the required minimum of 100 words. The following are the questions that are selected with the respective EVS variable numbers (i.e. V142)

v142/v144

v142 / v143: How important is it for you to live in a country that is governed democratically? And how democratically is this country being governed today? (Scales from 1 to 10)

Introduction text: Many people consider democracy a fundamental element of modern nation states, without our democratic foundations, governments would not pursue anymore the interest of the people. However, much depends from what we consider to be democratic.

CARI Question: When you think about democracy, what are its most important aspects for you?

CARI Question: Would you please elaborate on why they are so important for you?

CARI Question: Do you feel your country is currently governed democratically? Why?

v197

v197: People differ in what they think it means to be European. In your view, how important is it to share a European Culture?

Introduction: The European Union has enlarged a lot in the last decades; it now covers an area of 4 million square kilometres and includes 27 states. Given this variety, people differ in what they think it means to be European.

CARI Question: In your opinion, what does it mean to be European / a citizen of the European Union?

CARI Question: What characteristics would make you think that a person shares a European culture?

CARI Question: Would you say that you feel integrated in the European Community?

CARI Question: Can you describe what makes you feel integrated or not integrated in the European Community?

v31

v31: Generally speaking, would you say that most people can be trusted or that you can't be too careful in dealing with people? "Most people can be trusted" or "Need to be very careful"

Introduction: Trust is a multifaceted concept; consequently, almost everybody is motivated by different reasons for trusting other people.

CARI Question: From your point of view, what are the most important aspects that lead you to trust a person?

CARI Question: Can you describe what the reasons are that lead you to distrust a person?

CARI Question: Living in a society where it is easy to trust others makes every day's life easier, do you feel that you are living in a trustworthy / trusting society?

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